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**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCE AND
CRITICAL THINKING OF B.Ed STUDENTS.**

Education subject

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Abstract

The Aim Of The Study Was To Find Out The Relationship Between Multiple Intelligence And Critical Thinking Of B.Ed., Students In Tuticorin. The Sample Consists Of 250 B.Ed., Students . The Findings Showed That (I) There Is No Significant Difference Between Male And Female B.Ed., Trainees In Their Verbal- Linguistic, Logical-Mathematical, Visual-Spatial, Bodily-Kinesthetic, Musical-Rhythmic, Interpersonal, Intrapersonal And Naturalistic Intelligence (Ii) There Is No Significant Difference Between Male And Female B.Ed., Trainees In Their Critical Thinking (Iii) There Is No Significant Difference Among Boys, Girls And Co-Education B.Ed., Trainees And Their Verbal-Linguistic, Logical-Mathematics, Visual-Spatial, Bodily-Kinesthetic, Musical-Rhythmic, Interpersonal, Intrapersonal And Naturalistic Intelligence (Iv) There Is No Significant Difference Among Boys, Girls And Co-Education B.Ed., Trainees And Their Critical Thinking (V) There Is Significant Relationship Between Multiple Intelligence And Critical Thinking Of B.Ed., Trainees.

Introduction

Education Is The Creation Of Sound Mind In A Sound Body. Education Brings All Round Harmonious Development Of The Personality Of An Individual Such As Physical, Intellectual, Aesthetic, Social, Economic, Religious, Cultural, Spiritual And Through Such Development Of Individual Social Needs Can Be Realized.

Multiple Intelligence

Howard Gardner it is a set of skills allowing individuals to find and resolve genuine problems they face. Multiple intelligence included verbal- linguistic, logical, kinesthetic, spatial, musical, interpersonal, intrapersonal and naturalistic intelligence.

Critical Thinking

A mental process of analyzing or evaluating information. The information can be gathered from observation, experience, reasoning, or communication.

Significance Of The Study

Multiple intelligence its greatest contribution to education by suggesting that teachers need to expand their repertoire of techniques, tools and strategies beyond the typical linguistic and logical method. The theory of multiple intelligence functions not only as a remedy to one sidedness in teaching but also as a met model for organizing and synthesizing all the educational innovations that have sought to break out of the narrowly confines approach to learning.

Student teacher's ability to exercise and promote higher order thinking will impact student's ability to develop these thinking skills and abilities themselves. Given this premise, assessing the multiple intelligence of student teacher is most important. Therefore by providing baseline data pertaining to pre-service teachers, multiple intelligence would be beneficial to understand and dynamics in teaching-learning process.

Critical thinking is ideally an objective process used to determine the value of an argument, set of beliefs, claim or issue. Critical thinking usually employs logical reasoning and empirical evidence to reach a conclusion, and ultimately seeks to move away from personal biases, intuitions. Critical thinking is about being both willing and to think. Critical thinking is important for young people to develop and utilize good critical thinking, not just for their education but also life.

To improve student teacher performance on thinking skills, schools of education must improve training of student teacher with the help of both critical thinking and multiple intelligence. Both of these two things teach cognitive skills to pre-services teachers before training them to teach these skills in the class room. As student teacher learn to think more critically, they become more proficient at historical, scientific, and mathematical thinking. Finally, they develop skills, abilities, and values crucial to success in everyday life.

Objectives of the study

1. To find out the level of multiple intelligence of B.Ed., students.
2. To find out the level of critical thinking of B.Ed., students.
3. To find out whether any significant difference between male and female B.Ed., students in their multiple intelligence.
4. To find out whether any significant difference between male and female B.Ed., students in their critical thinking.
5. To find out whether there is any significant difference among men's, women's and co-education B.Ed., trainees and their multiple intelligence.
6. To find out whether there is any significant difference among men's, women's and co-

education B.Ed., trainees and their critical thinking.

7. To find out whether any significant relationship between multiple intelligence and critical thinking of the B.Ed., students.

Null Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed., students in their multiple intelligence.
2. There is no any significant difference between male and female B.Ed., students in their critical thinking.
3. To find out whether there is any significant difference among men's, women's and co-education B.Ed., trainees and their multiple intelligence.
4. To find out whether there is any significant difference among men's, women's and co-education B.Ed., trainees and their critical thinking.
5. There is no any significant relationship between multiple intelligence and critical thinking of the B.Ed., students.

Method Used For The Study

The investigator has adopted the survey method

Population For The Study

The population for the study was all the B.Ed., trainees in Tuticorin District.

Sample For The Study

The investigator has used random sampling technique for selecting the sample from the population. The sample consists of 250 students randomly selected from ten colleges of education in Tuticorin District, Tamil Nadu.

Tools Used

The following tools were used for data collection.

1. Adopted and validated Multiple intelligence inventory developed by Terry Armstrong
2. Adopted and validated Critical thinking inventory developed by Sylvan Barnat.

**TABLE 1
LEVEL OF MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCE AND CRITICAL THINKING
OF B.Ed., TRAINEES**

Variables	Level					
	Low		Average		High	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Multiple intelligence	25	24	53	51	26	25
Critical thinking	38	26	68	46.6	40	27.4

From the above table it is found that 25% of B.Ed trainees have low and 51% of B.Ed trainees have average and 25% of B.Ed trainees have high level of multiple intelligence and 26% of B.Ed trainees have low and 46% of B.Ed trainees have average and 27% of B.Ed trainees have high level of critical thinking.

NULL HYPOTHESIS 1.1

There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed., trainees in their multiple intelligence.

**TABLE 4.07
THE ‘t’ VALUE BETWEEN MALE AND FEMALE B.Ed., TRAINEES IN THEIR
MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCE**

S.No.	Dimensions	Male		Female		Calculated ‘t’ value	Remarks
		Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D		
1.	Linguistic intelligence	19.009	3.9866	18.472	3.8635	1.069	NS

2.	Logical intelligence	16.951	4.8679	16.753	4.8630	0.312	NS
3.	Spatial intelligence	21.221	4.9481	21.458	4.4305	0.391	NS
4.	Kinesthetic intelligence	18.250	4.3550	19.465	4.1757	0.027	NS
5.	Musical intelligence	19.009	5.3652	18.732	4.8838	0.424	NS
6.	Interpersonal intelligence	24.692	4.7807	23.869	5.1263	1.286	NS
7.	Intrapersonal intelligence	34.596	6.7787	35.137	6.6970	0.626	NS
8.	Naturalistic intelligence	24.519	5.8025	24.643	5.6711	0.170	NS
	Total	178.250	26.881	178.53	27.067	0.082	NS

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' value is 1.96)

From the above table it is inferred that there is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed., trainees in the dimensions of verbal-linguistic, logical- mathematical, visual-spatial, bodily-kinesthetic, musical-rhythmic, interpersonal, intrapersonal and naturalistic intelligence.

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed., trainees in their critical thinking.

**TABLE-4.15
THE 't' VALUE BETWEEN MALE AND FEMALE B.Ed., TRAINEES
IN THEIR CRITICAL THINKING**

Critical thinking	Male		Female		Calculate d 't' value	Remarks
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D		
		66.7788	9.74924	66.5205	10.74483	0.195

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' value is 1.96)

It is referred from the table that there is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed., trainees in their critical thinking.

**TABLE 4
THE 'F' VALUE BETWEEN MEN'S, WOMEN'S AND CO-EDUCATION B.Ed.,
TRAINEES AND THEIR MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCE**

S.No.	Dimensions	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Mean Square Variance	'F' value	Remarks
1.	Linguistic intelligence	Between	81.489	40.744	2.693	NS
		Within	3737.407	15.131		
2.	Logical intelligence	Between	16.872	8.436	0.356	NS
		Within	5855.404	23.706		
3.	Spatial intelligence	Between	126.479	63.239	0.053	NS
		Within	5245.121	21.235		
4.	Kinesthetic intelligence	Between	0.469	0.235	0.373	NS
		Within	155.375	0.629		
5.	Musical intelligence	Between	25.053	12.526	0.483	NS
		Within	6403.171	25.924		
6.	Interpersonal intelligence	Between	181.325	90.662	3.717	S
		Within	6024.439	24.390		
7.	Intrapersonal intelligence	Between	272.268	136.134	2.992	NS
		Within	10981.796	44.461		
8.	Naturalistic intelligence	Between	106.445	53.222	1.638	NS
		Within	8025.939	32.494		
	Total	Between	4275.454	2137.727	2.993	NS
		Within	176391.282	714.135		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 'F' value is 3.04)

It is referred from the table that there is no significant difference among men's, women's and co-education B.Ed., trainees and their verbal-linguistic, logical-mathematics, visual-spatial, bodily-kinesthetic, musical-rhythmic, intrapersonal and naturalistic intelligence, but there is significant difference among type of college of B.Ed., trainees and their interpersonal intelligence.

**TABLE 5
THE 'F' VALUE BETWEEN MEN'S, WOMEN'S AND CO-EDUCATION B.Ed.,
TRAINEES AND THEIR CRITICAL THINKING**

Critical thinking	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Mean Square Variance	'F' value	Remarks
	Between	2719.411	1359.706		
	Within	23814.993	96.417	14.102	S

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 'F' value is 3.04)

From the above table it is inferred that there is significant difference among men's, women's and co-education B.Ed., trainees and their critical thinking.

**TABLE 6
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCE AND CRITICAL
THINKING OF B.Ed., TRAINEES**

Multiple intelligence		Critical thinking		ΣXY	Table value	Calculated 'r' value	Remarks
ΣX	ΣX^2	ΣY	ΣY^2	1070899	0.139	0.350	S
15942	1039848	16657	1136357				

(At 5% level of significance the table value is 0.139)

From the above table it is inferred that there is significant relationship between multiple intelligence and critical thinking of B.Ed., trainees.

FINDINGS

1. 45.2% of rural and 51.6% of urban B.Ed., trainees have average level of multiple intelligence, 47.6% of rural and 47.6% of urban B.Ed., trainees have average level of critical thinking.
2. There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed., trainees in their verbal- linguistic, logical-mathematical, visual-spatial, bodily-kinesthetic, musical-rhythmic, interpersonal, intrapersonal and naturalistic intelligence.
3. There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed., trainees in their critical thinking.
4. There is no significant difference among men's, women's and co-education B.Ed.,

trainees and their verbal-linguistic, logical-mathematical, visual-spatial, bodily-kinesthetic, musical-rhythmic, intrapersonal and naturalistic intelligence, but there is significant difference between men's, women's and co-education B.Ed., trainees and their interpersonal intelligence.

5. There is significant difference among men's, women's and co-education B.Ed., trainees and their critical thinking.
6. There is significant relationship between multiple intelligence and critical thinking of B.Ed., trainees.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Teaching strategies should be developed for the development of different dimension of multiple intelligence.
2. Problem based teaching method can be adopted.
3. Group study methods should be encouraged in class rooms.
4. Intrapersonal abilities of future felicitators should be encouraged through counseling programmers.
5. Workshops and seminars may be conducted to student teachers to make them to understand the multiple intelligence of the learners.
6. Web-based teaching can be introduced to enhance the multiple intelligence.
7. Information and communication technology must be incorporated in teaching-learning process.
8. By playing brainstorming games which is used to develop critical thinking among the learners.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of the present investigation was to study the level of multiple intelligence and critical thinking with reference to some selected variables. This study indicated significant relationship among the variables. The study is found to be useful in the field of education.

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